

TIBBIYOTDA ISHLATILADIGAN IBORALAR VA AFORIZMLAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada lotin tilining tibbiyotda va tibbiyot mutaxassislari uchun ahamiyati haqida gap boradi. Hozirgi vaqtda kasbiy tilni shakllantirish tibbiyot xodimini tayyorlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Professional til asosan atamalar tizimidan hosil bo‘ladi. Barcha tibbiyot fanlari lotin tilidan foydalanishga asoslanishining bir qancha sabablari bor.

Kalit so‘zlar: dorivor xom ashyo, klinik atamalar, anatomik atamalar, terminologik elementlar, termin-shakllovchi elementlar, kimyoviy tarkibi, farmatsevtik terminologiya, nomenklatura

Kirish. Har qanday kasbni to‘liq o‘zlashtirish uchun odam o‘z mutaxassisligining terminologiyasini bilishi kerak. Evropa tarixi shunday rivojlanganki, ko‘pgina fanlarning, shu jumladan tibbiyotning asosiy terminologiyasi lotin va yunon tillarining so‘zlariga asoslanadi. Ammo, ehtimol, dunyo miqyosidagi ko‘p asrlik tajriba to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri shifokorning professional tilining tarkibiga ta‘sir qiladigan boshqa kasbiy faoliyat yo‘q, chunki tibbiyot va farmatsevtika sohasidagi mutaxassislarni tayyorlashda katta ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan fanlardan biri, shubhasiz, lotin tili bo‘lib, va bu tilni bilish kerak. Kundalik ish - kasalliklarning nomlarini, anatomik va klinik atamalarni, dorivor xom ashyoning nomlarini, kimyoviy birikmalar nomlarining xalqaro nomenklaturasida va ayniqsa formulada qabul qilingan botanika atamalarini o‘qiyotganda.

Asosiy qism. Zamonaviy shifokor, hatto professional mavzuda rus tilida gaplashganda ham, lotin va yunon tilidagi so‘zlarning 60% dan ortig‘ini ishlatadi. Va bu ajablanarli emas, chunki ma‘lumki, turli xil fanlarning terminologiyalari, shu jumladan nisbatan yaqinda paydo bo‘lganlar, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri yoki bilvosita, lug‘at va so‘zlarni shakllantirish vositalarini faol jalb qilish orqali to‘ldirilib, qadimgi dunyoning ushbu ikkita klassik tili sifatida to‘ldirishda davom etmoqda.

Tibbiy terminologiyaning tuzilishi. Zamonaviy tibbiyot terminologiyasi eng murakkab terminologik tizimlardan biridir. Tibbiy atamalarning umumiy soni

noma'lum - mutaxassislarning fikriga ko'ra, zamonaviy tibbiyotning terminologik fondi 500 ming tibbiy atamalardan oshadi. Agar yuz yil oldin bilimdon shifokor zamonaviy terminologiyani yaxshi bilgan bo'lsa, bugungi kunda bir necha yuz ming tibbiy atamalarni o'zlashtirish deyarli mumkin emas:

Tibbiyot terminologiyasi 3 xil yo'nalish bo'yicha farqlanadi:

1) Anatomik terminologiya. Bu tibbiyot ta'limining ajralmas qismidir, chunki barcha anatomik atamalar lotin tilida, anatomiya va lotin tili bo'limida parallel o'rganiladi. Bu yerda ikki bo'lim ikki nuqtai nazardan qaraladi:

a) Anatomiya nuqtai nazaridan bu termin ob'ekt bilan haqiqiy bog'lanish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega, anatomik hosil bo'lishi bu termin bilan chaqiriladi (yuz joylashgan joyda, uning vazifalari).

b) Lotin tili nuqtai nazaridan termin til bilan bog'liq holda muhim ahamiyatga ega (qanday stress, tugash, ibora).

Demak, shuni aytish mumkinki, anatomist mazmun bilan, lotinni esa termin shakli bilan tashvishga soladi.

2) Klinik terminologiya. Bu klinik amaliyotda qo'llaniladigan terminologiyadir. Klinik terminlarning aksariyati so'z hosil qiluvchi elementlardan hosil bo'lgan birikmalar so'zlaridir. Klinik terminologiyaning assimilyatsiyasida asosiy rolni yunoncha-lotinchacha termin-shakllovchi elementlar - terminologik elementlar o'ynaydi. Greko-lotin terminologik elementlari tizimini o'zlashtirish asosiy tibbiy klinik terminologiyani tushunishning bir xil terminologik kalitidir. Masalan, elementlar -rrhagia (qon ketish), -pexia (jarrohlik operatsiyasi: a'zoning to'g'rilanishi), entero- (ichak), nephro- (buyrak) atamasini bilish enterorrhagiya, enterorrhagia, nephrorrhagia, enteropexia, nephropexia va boshqalar kabi klinik terminlarni tushunishga imkon beradi. Klinik terminologik elementlarning (TE) umumiy soni 1500 dan ortiq bo'lsa-da, ular boshqa chastota darajasiga ega.

Eng faol termin elementlari soni 600 ga yaqin. Klinik terminologiyaning asosiy qismi 150 termin elementidan iborat bo'lib, undan tibbiy lug'atning asosiy qismi tuzilgan.

3) Farmatsevtik terminologiya. Bundan tashqari, unda asosan yunoncha va lotincha so'zlar, ya'ni ularning ayrim qismlari qo'llanadi, ulardan sun'iy ravishda yangi atamalar va nomlar tarkib topadi.

Dori-darmonlarning nomlari so'zlarning standart lotin va yun. atama elementlari (AE) bilan tuzilgan bo'lib, uning amaliy prinsipi, kimyoviy tarkibi,

asosiy komponentlari va boshqalar haqidagi ma'lumotlarni faqat dorining nomidan olish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Vaqt o'tishi bilan shifokorlar va boshqa tibbiyot xodimlari professional muloqotda milliy tillarga o'tishgan, ammo asosiy hukmronlik hali greko-lotin elementlariga, so'z va iboralarga tegishli. Bunga asosan ularning universal milliy xarakteri sabab bo'lgan. Shuning uchun kasalliklar, diagnostika va davolash usullarining nomlari har qanday tilda tan olinadi.

Lotin tili hozirda butun dunyodan kelgan shifokorlar va tibbiyot xodimlari tomonidan o'rganiladigan va qo'llaniladigan bir qator biomedik fanlar va nomenklaturalarda xalqaro ilmiy til sifatida ishlatiladi. Shuning uchun tibbiyot sohasida faoliyat yuritayotgan har qanday mutaxassis lotin tibbiyot terminologiyasining ta'lim va tushunish tamoyillari bilan tanish ekanligi mutlaqo ayon.

Barcha tibbiyot fanlarida: anatomiya, histologiya, embriologiya, mikrobiologiya, mikrobiologiya, patologik anatomiya va klinik fanlar, shuningdek farmakologiya sohasida nomzodlikning bu an'anasiga hech qachon to'xtalib o'tmagan va shu kungacha davom etmoqda.

Ammo nafaqat tibbiyotda lotincha so'zlar terminologiya va nomzodlik uchun xalqaro vosita sifatida o'z vazifasini saqlab qolgan. Lotin va lotinlashgan grekcha so'z va so'z elementlari hayotning barcha sohalaridagi barcha tillar tomonidan - kundalik nomlaridan “Bonaqua” va “automaton” dan tortib, “Tomograf”, “Sinxrofasotron” va ijtimoiy-siyosiy terminologiya atamalarigacha qo'llaniladi.

Lotin tili ham katta ahamiyatga ega, chunki u ko'plab lotin ildizlari o'tgan rus tilini yaxshiroq va chuqurroq tahlil qilishga yordam beradi, bu esa bir qator yangi so'zlarni yaratadi, masalan kommunizm, prezidium, kengash, kvorum, universitet va boshqalar.

Lotin tili ham katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan iboralar ham mavjuddir. Masalan: *Deest remedii locus ubi, guae vitia fuerunt, mores fiunt. Exitus letalis. Facile omnes, cum valemus, recta consilia aegrotis damus. Festina lente. Habitus aegroti. Ignoti nulla curatio morbi. Invia est in medicina via sine lingua Latina. In vino veritas, in aqua sanitas. Medicamenta heroica in manu imperiti sunt, ut gladius in dextra furiosi (in dextra manu). Medica mente, non medicamentis. Medice, cura te ipsum. Medicina fructosior ars nulla. Medicus nihi aliud est, quam animi consolatio. Medicus*

philosophus est; non enim multa est inter sapientiam et medicinam differentia. Melius est nomen bonum quam magnae divitiae.

Xulosa. Ushbu maqolada tibbiyot oliygozlari talabalari uchun lotin tilining va lotin tilidagi iboralarning ahamiyati haqida gap yuritilgan va lotin tili hozirda butun dunyodan kelgan shifokorlar va tibbiyot xodimlari tomonidan o‘rganiladigan va qo‘llaniladigan bir qator biomedik fanlar va nomenklaturalarda xalqaro ilmiy til sifatida ishlatilishi haqida tushuncha keltirilgan. Shuning uchun tibbiyot sohasida faoliyat yuritayotgan har qanday mutaxassis lotin tibbiyot terminologiyasining ta'lim va tushunish tamoyillarini o‘rganishi shart.

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